

Highlights

- Prescribed fires planning is crucial for *Pinus pinaster* Ait. recruitment dynamics
- Seeds from drier provenances performed better than those from more humid regions
- Burned seeds showed lower germination and survival rates
- In burned areas, fire-affected seeds displayed better germination and survival

1 **Regeneration of *Pinus pinaster* Aiton after prescribed fires: response to burn**
2 **timing and biogeographical seed provenance across a climatic gradient**

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12 **Abstract**

13 Prescribed fires are used as a fuel reduction tool, but heat alter microsite conditions
14 affecting the natural regeneration of Mediterranean pine forests. Our study tested the
15 hypothesis that implementing prescription before or after pine seed release may
16 influence the composition of tree communities by changing the regeneration patterns of
17 *Pinus pinaster* Aiton across a climatic gradient in the eastern Iberian Peninsula. We ran
18 a seed-sowing experiment to analyse the recruitment patterns of this pine species in
19 prescribed-burned stands, in two different biogeographical seed provenances from
20 wetter and drier areas than the local seeding site. Survival of seedlings was through one
21 year, until the end of the first drought and winter period, respectively. More than 5400
22 seeds were sown during the study distributed in sixty plots (30 burned, 30 unburned) per
23 site and treatment, with 10 seeding units per plot. General linear models (GLMs) and
24 ANOVA analyses indicated higher performance for the Drier seed provenance in
25 burned areas, whereas a similar performance was recorded in the control area. Control
26 areas showed higher germination and success rates for plant establishment throughout
27 the study period. Total germination and survival after one year were slightly higher,
28 respectively, at northern sites due to massive mortality during summer in the southern
29 stands. At the burned sites, the mean germination time was significantly longer in those
30 seeds sown before fire passage than those sown after fire. Total germination and
31 successful establishment were significantly higher in the individuals sown before the
32 passage of the fire than in those sown after fire. Most of the mortality occurred in
33 summer for the southern stand, while winter was the most constraining period at the
34 northern sites. The understanding of the dynamics in this species' establishment can
35 help managers to perform a better management planning according to the species'
36 ecology.

37 **Keywords:** Seed germination, seedling survival, Mediterranean pine forest, prescribed
38 fires-planning, ecological restoration, *Pinus pinaster* Aiton

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54 **1 Introduction**

55 The influence of forest fires as a major driver of landscape changes and ecosystem
56 dynamics is especially important in the Mediterranean Region (Keane et al., 2004;
57 Keeley et al., 2011). In the western Mediterranean Basin, dense fire-prone
58 undermanaged forest areas have increased due to rural abandonment in recent decades,
59 and continuous reforestation based mainly on drought-resistant conifers taking place in
60 the last century (Maestre and Cortina, 2004). The reduction in agricultural areas which,
61 in the past, have created a discontinued and patched landscape, has shaped many of
62 these conifer stands to become continuous forested areas of tens of thousands hectares
63 (Poyatos et al., 2009). These conditions have promoted a fuel load increase, which has
64 triggered large and high-severity fires throughout Mediterranean terrestrial ecosystems
65 (Barbero et al., 1990).

66 In Spain, Forest Services are progressively implementing prescribed fires as a forest-
67 management tool to reduce fuel load to reduce the risk of fire and decrease the surface
68 and severity of burned areas, if wildfire happens (Casals et al., 2016). In south Europe,
69 fire-prone ecosystems with the traditional use of fire in cultural landscapes set the
70 perfect scenario for implementing prescribed fires. However, factors like demography
71 distribution, socio-economic and land use limit this tool from being extended
72 (Fernandes et al., 2013). The main objective of prescribed burnings is to create a more
73 diverse landscape in fuel load terms and to support the fire regime to promote the
74 regeneration of fire-adapted (or dependent) species (Pollet and Omi, 2002). Prescription
75 is usually programmed outside the fire season, which raises some questions about the
76 effects and implications of this preventive tool in many key ecological processes, such
77 as litterfall biomass, predation, water repellency, soil respiration (Espinosa et al., 2018;

78 Plaza-Álvarez et al., 2017; Sagra et al., 2017). In addition, the fire intensity of most
79 controlled fires is lower than that reached in wildfires, which hinders the regeneration of
80 those species that have adapted to historical fire regimes (Pausas and Fernández-Muñoz,
81 2012). Adaptive fire traits in Mediterranean species are normally exaptations to dry
82 seasons (Keeley et al., 2011; Knapp et al., 2009). This may influence regeneration and
83 recruitment dynamics, which may induce changes in other ecosystem processes.
84 Adaptive responses of Mediterranean pines to fire are well-known. *Pinus pinaster* Aiton
85 has serotinous cones that disperse seeds after fires (de las Heras et al., 2012; Retana et
86 al., 2012). Planning the sustainable management of these ecosystems is increasingly
87 challenging because of climate change (Adger, 2000). Forest management strategies
88 rely on predictable tree regeneration to ensure ecosystem persistence and resilience.
89 Moreover, climate change is expected to increase summer drought length and intensity
90 affecting wildfire regimen (IPCC, 2013). This may thus reduce the success of natural
91 regeneration by requiring adjustments to be made to silvicultural practices (Bravo-
92 Oviedo et al., 2014).

93 The first development stages of trees are known to be one of the most limiting stages in
94 the life of stands. Natural germination and early establishment are the most constraining
95 and the most critical mechanisms in shaping the forest structure (Dalling et al., 2002).
96 There are many issues that restrain the establishment of new individuals, and the
97 interactions among them often make it difficult to identify the actual reasons for failure
98 (Adili et al., 2013; Manso et al., 2013). Changes in these environmental conditions, due
99 to either climate change or occurrence of natural disturbances like wildfires, make it
100 even more necessary to use adapted species, provenances and genotypes, which are
101 more resilient to these upcoming fluctuations (Alía et al., 1997a; Garzón et al., 2011;
102 Ghalambor et al., 2007). Natural ground fires, as well as prescribed fires, can alter

103 ecosystem conditions by limiting or promoting the establishment of regeneration.
104 Previous works have also suggested that conifer recruitment may benefit by prescribed
105 burns (Ryan et al., 2013). At the same time, temperatures from prescribed fires may
106 trigger the dissemination of seeds of serotinous pines. It is known that some seeds need
107 calorific scarification to achieve better germination success (Ferrandis et al., 1999;
108 Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1995). However in many cases, those seeds affected by high
109 temperatures obtain lower germination rates (Alvarez et al., 2007). Predation can also
110 play an important role in these early stages (Sagra et al., 2017). as rodents and birds can
111 account for great seed and seedling losses which may constrain successful regeneration
112 (Lucas-Borja et al., 2010; Ordóñez et al., 2004). Prescribed fires can affect population
113 dynamics by altering canopy cover, soil nutrients, soil moisture, water repellence and
114 infiltration rates. These changes take place especially on the most superficial soil layer
115 and soil-litter interface, where seeds germinate and seedling growth takes place (Ryan et
116 al., 2013). Severe fires are known negatively to impact on maritime pine recruitment.
117 Temperatures above 120-150°C significantly lower the likelihood of germination
118 (Alvarez et al., 2005; Reyes and Casal, 2004). Crown or high severity fires can reduce
119 germination and seedling establishment compared to ground or low severity fires, which
120 meaningfully affect post-burn recruitment (Martínez et al., 2002). Although *Pinus*
121 *pinaster* dissemination may benefit by fire, seed germination is not heat-stimulated
122 (Escudero et al., 1999; Ferrandis et al., 1996; Martínez et al., 2002). *Pinus pinaster*
123 serotiny has been reported to be very location-dependant, with variations from 0-100%
124 of serotinous cones and trees depending on population (Fernandes and Rigolot, 2007;
125 Tapias et al., 2004). Tapias et al. (2004) have indicated the serotiny level in 26 *Pinus*
126 *pinaster*, locations and found a high serotiny in southern locations with drier and
127 warmer climates.

128 The effect of ash on a post-fire germination and early survival in pine species is
129 negative (Ne'eman et al., 1993; Reyes and Casal, 2004). The increase in nutrients
130 availability have been reported in severe fires (Pereira et al., 2012). Such increases can
131 also promote seedling growth (Mason et al., 2003). Although many studies have been
132 carried out about the influence of natural fires on the regeneration and early
133 establishment of Mediterranean pines, very little is known about the impacts of
134 prescribed fires can have on the regeneration stages. In the Iberian peninsula, more than
135 3 million ha have been reforested with *Pinus pinaster* in the last century. Its phenotypic
136 plasticity has promoted its success in a broader area than other species, and also its
137 suitability for growth in land protection and production (Alía et al., 1997).

138 The general goal of this study was to assess how prescribed burnings can affect the
139 early natural recruitment of a broadly geography-ranging Mediterranean pine species,
140 *Pinus pinaster* Aiton, to provide essential information to be used in forest management
141 programmes in south Europe. To do so, a) we tested seed germination and seedling
142 growth responses over an ombroclimate gradient by comparing treated (i.e. burned) and
143 control (intact) pine stands in three locations with different rainfall conditions; b) we
144 also analysed the effect of burning timing in relation to seed dispersal timing (where
145 timing is understood the time when prescribed fire and sowing were carried out); c) and
146 ecotype (i.e., dry *versus* wet seed geographical provenances) on pine recruitment
147 responses to make efficient decisions to design prescribed burning programmes. Our
148 hypotheses were: a) *Pinus pinaster* regeneration should perform somewhat worse on the
149 Humid climate which is slightly out of its natural range, b) implementing prescription
150 before or after pine seed release may influence may change regeneration patterns, and c)
151 Dry provenances should have better rates of germination and survival.

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153 **2 Material and Methods**

154 **Study area**

155 We studied *Pinus pinaster* post-burning early regeneration by sowing pine seeds in
156 three different sites located across a climatic gradient (Climate) in the eastern Iberian
157 Peninsula (Figure 1a): (i) a northern site in a humid climate (Humid); (ii) a central site
158 in a subhumid climate (Subhumid); (iii) a southern site located in a dry climate (Dry)
159 (Table 1).

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161 Figure 1. a) Location of the three study sites in the Iberian Peninsula; b) example of the
162 location of the study plots at each site; c) distribution of seeding units in a plot; d)
163 schematic illustration of a seeding unit in a burned area with Pre (simulating dispersion
164 prior to fire) and Post (simulating dispersion postfire); and Drier and Wetter
165 provenances. Terms are as described in the text.

166 Table 1. Description of the three sites located across the ombroclimate gradient. Mean
 167 annual temperature (MET); Mean lowest temperatures of the coldest month (ML);
 168 Mean highest temperatures of the hottest month (MH).

Characteristics	Humid site	Subhumid site	Dry site
Type of stand	Pure <i>Pinus nigra</i> stand	<i>Pinus nigra</i> and <i>Pinus pinaster</i> mixed stand	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> and <i>Pinus halepensis</i> mixed stand
Location	Beteta (40°33'02.9"N 2°06'32.6"W)	El Pozuelo (40°33'53.5"N 2°16'30.4"W)	Lezuza (38°54'21.9"N 2°20'13.9"W)
Annual precipitation (mm)	946	700	456
MET; ML; MH (°C)	10.2; 1.7; 20.1	11.3; 2.7; 23	13.5; -0.9; 31.8
Altitudinal range (m.a.s.l.)	1250 - 1300	1000 - 1050	1010 – 1040
Understory species	<i>Genista scorpius</i> L. <i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> L. <i>Juniperus communis</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Amelanchier ovalis</i> Medik. <i>Lavandula</i> sp. <i>Thymus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Cistus laurifolius</i> L. <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Genista Scorpius</i> L.	<i>Quercus ilex</i> subsp. <i>ballota</i> <i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Quercus coccifera</i> L. <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L. <i>Thymus</i> sp. <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.
Tree density (trees/ha)	1281 ±256	667 ±125	595 ±141
DBH (cm)	20.6 ±12.7	18.7 ±8.7	19.3 ±11.2
Average height (m)	7.25 ±3.27	7.49 ±3.68	5.25 ±1.9
Soil type	Clay	Sandy-loam	Clay
Slope (%)	10 ± 2	5 ± 2	4 ± 1
Aspect	Northeast	North	Northwest
Prescribed burn soil-litter interface T° (°C)	361±29	264±62	260±25

170 ***Experimental design***

171 In each stand, we set six square plots (50 m side, 2,500 m²), where we defined 30-m
172 side (900 m²) inner square plots to prevent the edge effect of fire. Three plots were not
173 burned (control), and three were treated by implementing prescribed burning (Figure
174 1b). All six plots were set in a homogeneous area with similar characteristics as to stand
175 structure and composition to prevent the influence of uncontrolled variables. We made a
176 thorough characterisation of plots to ensure relative homogeneity in variables such as:
177 slope, aspect, tree density, tree diameter, tree age, forest cover, tree species, shrubs
178 cover and shrubs/herbaceous species. Prescribed fires were performed by the Fire
179 Extinction Services of Castilla-La Mancha in the spring of 2016 to control the fuel load
180 and to prevent wildfires. Burning temperatures were monitored using HOBO
181 thermocouple type K (0°C-1,250°C (±4.0°C)) with insulated 30-AWG wire (less than
182 0.2 cm in diameter) assembled on Data Loggers UX120-014M (Onset Corp., Bourne
183 (MA), Australia). This instrument helped to analyse fire intensity and was placed on the
184 litter surface, on the soil surface and at 2-cm depth.

185 In each plot, 10 squared seeding units were randomly established (30-cm side; Figure
186 1c). The experimental design included three different treatments: seeding in unburned
187 plots (Control), pre-fire seeding (Pre, simulating seed dispersal before fire prescription)
188 and post-fire seeding (Post, simulating seed dispersal after fire prescription). Controls
189 were made up of seeding units installed in unburned areas to keep track of natural
190 germination and establishment rates. Pre and Post were installed on burned areas
191 immediately before the prescribed burn and just after burning, respectively. Each
192 seeding unit thus comprised two subsamples (containing 10 pine seeds of *Pinus pinaster*
193 each): one sown before and the other after fire passage, to check how fire would affect
194 the pine seeds naturally disseminated before and after fire, respectively (Figure 1d). In

195 addition, each subsample was composed of two different biogeographical seed
196 provenances of *Pinus pinaster* to check the responses related to climate adaption
197 depending on the study site. Provenance, defined as a territory with uniform ecological
198 conditions in which seed sources or stands have similar phenotypic or genetic
199 characteristics, were chosen from the available store of the Department of Forest
200 Genetic Resources of the Spanish Ministry of the Environment (Alía et al., 2005). Thus
201 we selected *Pinus pinaster* seeds from a provenance that came from a colder and more
202 humid region (Wetter: ES09 from Soria, north Spain) and another one from a hotter and
203 more arid area (Drier: ES18 from Moratalla, southeast Spain). Viability tests were
204 provided from the supplier (98% and 92%, respectively, for Wetter and Drier). In May
205 2016, ten maritime pine seeds of each provenance were manually sown at the soil-litter
206 interface in each replicate of all the seeding units to obtain the same standards in the
207 process in both burned and control plots following similar procedures carried for this
208 kind of study (Lucas-Borja et al., 2010). Small pits, with a 3-cm separation between
209 rows, were dug with a nail at a depth of less than 0.5 cm on the soil surface, and one
210 seed was placed. Seeding units were covered with fixed wire cages to prevent
211 seed/seedling predation (Sagra et al., 2017). Monitoring was carried out for more than 1
212 year after seeding by subsequent (2-3 months interval) counts from May 2016 to June
213 2017. During each sampling, the number of new pine seeds germinated from the
214 previous counting and the survival pine seedlings were recorded by monitoring each
215 individual grid. In this way, a sequential temporal track of the germination and
216 establishment of pine seedlings was obtained.

217 To characterise the germination of pine seeds and the survival of pine seedlings, and to
218 relate them with the studied factors (climatic gradient, provenance and burning
219 treatment) within each seeding unit, we calculated the germination rate as the number of

220 germinated seeds of the 10 sown seeds (GERMend). Germination was considered when
221 the geotropic radicle was visible. Likewise, the index mean germination time was
222 obtained (MGT, in days), defined as (1) (Bewley and Black, 1994).

$$223 \quad MGT = \sum_i \frac{(n_i * d_i)}{N} \quad (1)$$

224 where n_i is the number of germinated seeds; d_i is the time after sowing began (in days); and N is
225 the total number of sown seeds.

226 The success of establishment index (SOE, %) was calculated as the percentage of
227 seedlings alive after summer (SOEsummer) and at the end of the study (SOEend, %).
228 For the first index the number of seedlings alive after summer was compared with those
229 that had germinated before summer. For the latter, the percentage between the number
230 of pine seeds alive at the end of the study and the total number pine seeds that had
231 germinated throughout the study was calculated. Finally, the survival rate was also
232 calculated to keep track of the periodical dying rates of seedlings. This parameter
233 (SURVIVAL) was assessed as the number of pine seedlings that were still alive after 1
234 experimental year from those germinated during the study .

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236 *Statistical analyses*

237 Generalised linear models (GLMs) were used to evaluate the effects of factors and their
238 interactions: Treatment: Control, burned after pine seed dispersal (PRE), burned before
239 pine seed dispersal (POST); Provenance: Drier and Wetter; and Climatic gradient: Dry,
240 Subhumid, Humid. Significant ($P < 0.05$) effects were tested with one, two- and three-
241 way analyses of variance (ANOVA). The adjusted R-squared statistic was used, which
242 is more suitable than R^2 for comparing models with different numbers of independent

243 variables; F-value and the Durbin-Watson statistic to test the residuals to determine if
244 there was any significant correlation based on the order in which they occurred in the
245 data file. *Tukey's HSD (honest significant difference)* method was used to create
246 confidence intervals for all the pair-wise differences between factor levels means. To
247 perform these statistics R version 3.4.3 statistical software (Development Core Team
248 2017) and Statgraphics Centurion XV, version 15.1.02 (StatPoint Inc., 2005), were
249 used.

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252 **3 Results**

253 The GLM test (Table 2) revealed that Climate, Treatment and Provenance were
254 significant for all the variables, as were most of their interactions. Three variables
255 GERMend, SOEsummer and SOEend, showed significant responses to all the factors
256 and for most interactions. The adjusted R^2 was higher than 48 for all the models (Table
257 2). The significant factors of the model were run in an ANOVA, which illustrated
258 significantly high germination rates and higher SOEs for the Control plots (Table 3).
259 The burned plots also showed a significant difference between the maritime pine seeds
260 sown in the Pre and Post ones for GERMend and both the SOE rates. The pine seeds
261 from the Drier provenance also performed better than those from the Wetter one, with
262 significant differences for the four variables.

263 Table 2: General Linear Models for the variables in the study. Mean germination time in
264 days (MGT); number of pine seeds germinated at the end of the experiment (GERM);
265 success of establishment after summer (SOEsummer) (i.e., percentage of pine seeds that
266 survived the first dry period in relation to the number of pine seeds germinated
267 immediately before the dry period); SOEend: final success of establishment (i.e.,
268 number of pine seeds -out of 10 seeds per factor- that survived until the end of the

269 experiment in relation to the number of pine seeds germinated for that specific factor).

270 Significance is consider for a P-value under 0.05.

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		Factor	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	F	P
MGT						
R ²	53.15	Climate	6607.27	2	280.31	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	52.44	Treatment	2584.94	2	109.67	<0.001
F	85.01	Provenance	2706.37	1	146.94	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	4575.03	4	97.05	<0.001
Durbin-Watson	0.93	Treatment*Provenance	167.56	2	3.55	0.0293
		Climate*Treatment*Provenance	189.383	4	4.02	0.0186
GERMend						
R ²	49.8222	Climate	114.809	2	17.73	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	48.9685	Treatment	783.17	2	120.96	<0.001
F	58.36	Provenance	668.512	1	206.5	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Provenance	28.3879	2	4.38	0.0129
Durbin-Watson	1.60986	Treatment*Provenance	107.228	2	16.56	<0.001
SOEsummer						
R ²	51.74	Climate	175580	2	397.63	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	49.81	Treatment	9472.45	2	10.73	<0.001
F	54.49	Provenance	33865.9	1	76.69	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	5543.71	4	6.28	0.002
Durbin-Watson	1.05	Provenance*Provenance	6715.16	2	7.6	<0.001
		Climate*Provenance	6218.15	2	7.04	0.001
SOEend						
R2	49.1	Climate	52664	1	202.79	<0.001
Adjusted R2	48.24	Treatment	3089.48	2	5.95	0.0028
F	56.81	Provenance	1220.4	1	4.7	0.0306
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	11944.9	2	23	<0.001
Durbin-Watson	0.92	Treatment*Provenance	3538.99	2	6.81	0.0012
		Climate*Provenance	3625.22	1	13.96	<0.001

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279 Table 3: One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the significant factors. Means and
 280 standard errors are shown for each column. Different small letters indicate significant
 281 differences (P-value under 0.05) between the means of groups for each variable
 282 (Tukey's HSD method). Climate: Dry, Subhumid and Humid; Treatment: Control, Pre
 283 and Post; Provenance: Drier and Wetter.

FACTOR	VARIABLE			
Climate		Dry	Subhumid	Humid
	MGT	9.52±0.41b	18.82±0.43a	17.97±0.43a
	GERMend	6.34±0.2b	7.35±0.18a	7.3±0.17a
	SOEsummer	40.18±1.82b	86.5±1.21a	84.35±1.52a
	SOEend	10.53±0.91c	39.39±1.62a	34.72±1.5b
Treatment	VARIABLE	Control	Pre	Post
	MGT	19.04±0.46a	15.34±0.51b	11.94±0.47c
	GERMend	8.36±0.13a	7.18±0.17b	5.43±0.19c
	SOEsummer	77.44±1.59a	70.13±2.34b	63.46±2.48b
	SOEend	40.15±1.73a	27.93±1.54b	16.56±1.22c
Provenance	VARIABLE	Drier	Wetter	
	MGT	17.68±0.39a	13.2±0.42b	
	GERMend	8.1±0.12a	5.88±0.16b	
	SOEsummer	78.26±1.59a	62.42±1.88b	
	SOEend	32.7±1.39a	23.72±1.28b	

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285 Mean germination time indicated a longer germination time for all the control sites,
 286 with 19.04 days. Within the Burned areas, germination in the Pre treatments took longer

287 than in Post, except for the Dry climate, where no difference was observed (Figure 2a).
 288 Drier provenance took longer to germinate in the Pre burned seeds, while Wetter ones
 289 showed similar Pre and Post rates (Figure 2b). In Figure 2c we can observe no
 290 significant differences for MGT between the Control and both Burned treatments for the
 291 Drier provenance in the Humid and Subhumid climates, whereas the Dry climate
 292 showed a longer germination period for the Control seeds. The Wetter provenance
 293 showed similar germination periods for Dry and Subhumid, while Humid showed
 294 significantly lower MGT for POST.
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 298 Figure 2. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the interaction
 299 between the variable mean germination time (MGT) and the significant factors and
 300 interactions: site (CLIMATE), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in

301 the three Burned pine stands in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain.
 302 Different small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups
 303 (Tukey's HSD method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described
 304 in the text.

305 Figure 3a indicates the number of pine seeds germinated at the end of the study period
 306 (GERMend). There was a clear pattern, with a larger number of germinated pine seeds
 307 for the Drier provenances in the three climates. Moreover, GERMend showed no
 308 difference for treatments in the Drier provenance, while Wetter obtained a lower
 309 germination rate in Post when compared with Drier (Figure 3b).

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312 Figure 3. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the significant
 313 interaction between the variables GERMend and the significant factors and interactions:
 314 site (CLIMATE), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in the three
 315 Burned pine stands in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain. Different small
 316 letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups (Tukey's HSD
 317 method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described in the text.

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320 Figure 4. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the significant interaction between the variables SOEsummer and SOEend
321 and the significant factors and interactions: site (STAND), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in the three Burned pine stands
322 in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain. Different small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups
323 (Tukey's HSD method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described in the text.

324 Survival after the first summer was higher at the northern sites (Humid and Subhumid),
325 with the Drier provenance showing higher survival rates than the Wetter one. As seen in
326 Figure 4c, all the Drier seedlings were still alive in larger numbers for the three sites.
327 Survival after 1 study year (SOEend) was lower for the Burned areas in Humid and
328 Subhumid. In the Burned areas, the pine seedlings survival rates were lower in Post than
329 in Pre (Figure 4).

330 Figure 5 showed the temporal changes in SURVIVAL by indicating the number of
331 maritime pine seeds that were still alive for each factor (maximum of 10 seeds per
332 factor). The results evidenced worse performance in the Wetter provenances for each
333 site and treatment. Regarding the effect of treatments, the control lines in the figure
334 were often above the burned lines, which indicates more successful establishment for
335 the pine seeds not exposed to any treatment.

336 At the Burned sites, the fire-exposed pine seeds (PRE) showed a high survival rate for
337 all months, as opposed to those sown after fire passage (POST). This survival pattern
338 was recorded for the three sites and for both provenances. When comparing the three
339 stands, both northern stands (Humid and Subhumid) displayed a similar trend; i.e. a
340 high mortality rate after winter. Conversely, in the southern stand (Dry), the most
341 constraining period was summer.

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345 Figure 5: Number of maritime pine seedlings alive per period. Terms are as described in
 346 the text.

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349 4 Discussion

350 Research on prescribed fire management is a priority for Mediterranean terrestrial
 351 ecosystems in the global change scenario (Doblas-Miranda et al., 2015). The climate
 352 gradient design used here allowed us to evaluate three different scenarios for *Pinus*
 353 *pinaster* in this global change context. The soil temperatures monitored during the
 354 prescribed burning showed that the fire had low-intensity. However, temperatures were
 355 above the thresholds (60-120 °C) reported as being influential on the germination and
 356 survival dynamics of *Pinus pinaster* (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 1995; Reyes and Casal,

357 1995). Many ecological effects related to early seedling recruitment have been recorded
358 in the short term and in the same plots as this study. Some of these parameters are soil
359 respiration, water repellency, predation and litterfall (Espinosa et al., 2018; Plaza-
360 Álvarez et al., 2017; Sagra et al., 2017). The relationship between the climate features
361 associated with the provenance of *Pinus pinaster* seeds, and their survival rates,
362 suggests the use of provenances or breedings to better adapt to climate change (Alía et
363 al., 1997b). In our study, the pine seeds from the Drier provenance showed higher total
364 germination and survival rates than those found in Wetter. However, this could not be
365 related to fire intensity because the differences between Control plots and both
366 prescription timings (Pre and Post) were not significant. The higher GERMend and SOE
367 rates of the Drier provenance would be a response to drought conditions in summer,
368 which were harsher at the Dry site.

369 Our results showed a greater likelihood of establishment for a provenance from a more
370 arid and warmer climate than the study location, when comparing treatments and sites.
371 The consideration of these adaptive traits can enhance survival possibilities in a future
372 scenario, as predicted by IPCC (Garzón et al., 2011). Furthermore, as the response to
373 stress of *Pinus pinaster* is seasonal (Medlyn et al., 2002), more research on the effects
374 of prescription is needed; i.e. burns in autumn when *Pinus pinaster* also has natural
375 dispersion (Tapias et al., 2001). Although conserving natural forest genetic pools should
376 be a priority, lack of genetic identity due to the massive repopulation origin of these
377 stands would make the use of non-native individuals a possible strategy for facilitating
378 adaptation to global change in certain circumstances (Millar et al., 2007; PRUS, 1971;
379 Willis et al., 2010)..

380 Under favoured conditions, fire can promote *Pinus pinaster* germination (Calvo et al.,
381 2008). However, our analysis showed higher germination, a longer mean germination

382 time and better establishment success in three control areas. In fact prescribed burning
383 affected soil properties in the short term; i.e. soil moisture and soil respiration
384 diminished, while soil temperature increased (Plaza-Álvarez et al., 2017). These
385 changes play an important role on the seed performance, mainly in the first weeks after
386 seeding, when pine seed and seedling requirements for emergence and survival are
387 stricter (Gómez et al., 2004). These restrictions are also intensified by both the effect of
388 burning and summer drought (Madrigal et al., 2004; Padilla and Pugnaire, 2007).
389 Likewise, a negative response of *Pinus pinaster* seedlings to scrub removal by fire has
390 been reported in another study (Rodríguez-García et al., 2011). The lowest values for
391 the survival and germination rates were found in the Post seeding units, which agrees
392 with those studies that have indicated that ash accumulates after fire as a restrictive
393 factor for recruitment in pine species (Izhaki et al., 2000; Ne'eman et al., 1993; Vega et
394 al., 2008). Reyes and Casal, 2004, have observed that the larger amount of ash, the more
395 negative the effect on the germination of four pine species, including *Pinus pinaster*. In
396 our case both the Pre and Post seeds and seedlings were exposed to ash. However, ash
397 seemed to act as a limiting factor on seed germination and seedling survival, only on the
398 individuals sown after fire (mimicking dispersion during fire). Therefore, serotinous
399 provenances may be more negatively affected by ash compared to those disseminated
400 before prescribed fire. Severe wildfires can increase nutrient availability and enhance
401 seedling growth (Eugenio et al., 2006). However, low-severity wildfires may induce
402 such an important increase in nutrients and water-extractable elements (Pereira et al.,
403 2012).

404 Regarding site effect, we found that the germination values and survival indicators at
405 the southern site were lower than those at the two northern ones, which had similar
406 survival rates in year 1 after fire. However, although there were fewer germinated pine

407 seeds at the Dry site, the number of seedlings observed for SOEsummer and SOEend
408 was similar to that in the Humid and Subhumid areas. In the first summer, the survival
409 of the pine seedlings at the Dry site was approximately half that in the two other
410 localities (where about 85% of all the seeds germinated), and showed large differences
411 for SOEend (less than 1/3 in Dry than in Humid and Subhumid). Enough soil moisture
412 and seed hydration allow seedlings to grow deeper root systems and can increase their
413 survival chance, which also corroborates the worse performance we observed at the
414 burned sites, which was more noticeable after the summer drought in the Dry plots (Lee
415 et al., 2004). In contrast, snow and cold temperatures may act as a limiting factor for
416 seedling survival at Humid and Subhumid sites.

417 Our initial hypothesis about better performance of the Drier provenance at Burned sites
418 was not verified due to the similar patterns found in both the Burned and Control areas.
419 This record may be attributable to the exaptation of the Drier provenance to the climatic
420 conditions in the study area. This can be an indicator of future possible scenarios of
421 *Pinus pinaster* recruitment dynamics in the climate change context, which would be
422 crucial for forest management decision making. Discerning the effect of prescribed
423 burns and climate conditions on provenance selection would need a more controlled
424 environment, such as ecotron or similar experiments (Lindner and Kolström, 2009).

425

426 **5 Conclusions**

427 This study offers valuable information about the effects and consequences of prescribed
428 fires as a tool for managing maritime pine forests. The use of fire needs to be well
429 planned according to species phenology to match it to natural seed dissemination. We
430 conclude that when the purpose of the controlled fire is to promote the regeneration of

431 new *Pinus pinaster* individuals, prescription should be carried out before natural pine
432 seed dispersal. Moreover, when stand regeneration is a major concern, dismissing fire
433 due lower germination and survival in burned areas could be considered. In contrast,
434 prescribed fires would be a proper tool when the management goal is to produce fire
435 breaks by simultaneously diminishing biomass and regeneration. The climatic gradient
436 indicated that both the germination and early survival of *Pinus pinaster* in Humid and
437 Subhumid areas could be more successful than in a Dry climate. The use of different
438 provenances to enhance performance in climate change scenarios would be desirable,
439 although information about how provenances may properly match prescribed-fire
440 management should be improved and should include studies where precipitation or
441 temperature would be control factors. Knowledge is still missing to assume that
442 provenances from drier areas perform better and, thus, more research with different
443 species and provenances can be decisive to improve adaptive forest management and
444 the use of prescribed fire.

445

446

447 **Acknowledgements**

448 The authors thank the Castilla-La Mancha Forest Service for carrying out the prescribed
449 fires. Also to Helen Warburton for reviewing the English. Javier Sagra was supported
450 by a Doctoral fellowship from the Internal Research Plan of the University of Castilla–
451 La Mancha, co-financed by the European Social Fund. This work was also funded by
452 the Spanish Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA)
453 awarding the National Research Project GEPRIF (RTA2014-00011-C06). RAS is
454 supported by a Postdoctoral grant from Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and
455 Competitiveness (Juan de la Cierva-Formación-FJCI-2015-26848).

456

457

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Table 1. Description of the three sites located across the ombroclimate gradient. Mean annual temperature (MET); Mean lowest temperatures of the coldest month (ML); Mean highest temperatures of the hottest month (MH).

Characteristics	Humid site	Subhumid site	Dry site
Type of stand	Pure <i>Pinus nigra</i> stand	<i>Pinus nigra</i> and <i>Pinus pinaster</i> mixed stand	<i>Pinus pinaster</i> and <i>Pinus halepensis</i> mixed stand
Location	Beteta (40°33'02.9"N 2°06'32.6"W)	El Pozuelo (40°33'53.5"N 2°16'30.4"W)	Lezuza (38°54'21.9"N 2°20'13.9"W)
Annual precipitation (mm)	946	700	456
MET; ML; MH (°C)	10.2; 1.7; 20.1	11.3; 2.7; 23	13.5; -0.9; 31.8
Altitudinal range (m.a.s.l.)	1250 - 1300	1000 - 1050	1010 – 1040
Understory species	<i>Genista scorpius</i> L. <i>Arctostaphylos uva-ursi</i> L. <i>Juniperus communis</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Amelanchier ovalis</i> Medik. <i>Lavandula</i> sp. <i>Thymus</i> sp.	<i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Cistus laurifolius</i> L. <i>Berberis vulgaris</i> L. <i>Rosa canina</i> L. <i>Genista Scorpius</i> L.	<i>Quercus ilex</i> subsp. <i>ballota</i> <i>Quercus faginea</i> Lam. <i>Quercus coccifera</i> L. <i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L. <i>Thymus</i> sp. <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.
Tree density (trees/ha)	1281 ±256	667 ±125	595 ±141
DBH (cm)	20.6 ±12.7	18.7 ±8.7	19.3 ±11.2
Average height (m)	7.25 ±3.27	7.49 ±3.68	5.25 ±1.9
Soil type	Clay	Sandy-loam	Clay
Slope (%)	10 ± 2	5 ± 2	4 ± 1
Aspect	Northeast	North	Northwest
Prescribed burn soil-litter interface T° (°C)	361±29	264±62	260±25

Table 2: General Linear Models for the variables in the study. Mean germination time in days (MGT); number of pine seeds germinated at the end of the experiment (GERM); success of establishment after summer (SOEsummer) (i.e., percentage of pine seeds that survived the first dry period in relation to the number of pine seeds germinated immediately before the dry period); SOEend: final success of establishment (i.e., number of pine seeds -out of 10 seeds per factor- that survived until the end of the experiment in relation to the number of pine seeds germinated for that specific factor). Significance is considered for a P-value under 0.05.

		Factor	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	F	P
MGT						
R ²	53.15	Climate	6607.27	2	280.31	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	52.44	Treatment	2584.94	2	109.67	<0.001
F	85.01	Provenance	2706.37	1	146.94	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	4575.03	4	97.05	<0.001
Durbin-Watson	0.93	Treatment*Provenance	167.56	2	3.55	0.0293
		Climate*Treatment*Provenance	189.383	4	4.02	0.0186
GERMend						
R ²	49.8222	Climate	114.809	2	17.73	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	48.9685	Treatment	783.17	2	120.96	<0.001
F	58.36	Provenance	668.512	1	206.5	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Provenance	28.3879	2	4.38	0.0129
Durbin-Watson	1.60986	Treatment*Provenance	107.228	2	16.56	<0.001
SOEsummer						
R ²	51.74	Climate	175580	2	397.63	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	49.81	Treatment	9472.45	2	10.73	<0.001
F	54.49	Provenance	33865.9	1	76.69	<0.001
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	5543.71	4	6.28	0.002
Durbin-Watson	1.05	Provenance*Provenance	6715.16	2	7.6	<0.001
		Climate*Provenance	6218.15	2	7.04	0.001
SOEend						
R ²	49.1	Climate	52664	1	202.79	<0.001
Adjusted R ²	48.24	Treatment	3089.48	2	5.95	0.0028
F	56.81	Provenance	1220.4	1	4.7	0.0306
P-value	<0.001	Climate*Treatment	11944.9	2	23	<0.001
Durbin-Watson	0.92	Treatment*Provenance	3538.99	2	6.81	0.0012
		Climate*Provenance	3625.22	1	13.96	<0.001

Table 3: One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) of the significant factors. Means and standard errors are shown for each column. Different small letters indicate significant differences (P-value under 0.05) between the means of groups for each variable (Tukey's HSD method). Climate: Dry, Subhumid and Humid; Treatment: Control, Pre and Post; Provenance: Drier and Wetter.

FACTOR	VARIABLE			
Climate		Dry	Subhumid	Humid
	MGT	9.52±0.41b	18.82±0.43a	17.97±0.43a
	GERMend	6.34±0.2b	7.35±0.18a	7.3±0.17a
	SOEsummer	40.18±1.82b	86.5±1.21a	84.35±1.52a
	SOEend	10.53±0.91c	39.39±1.62a	34.72±1.5b
Treatment		Control	Pre	Post
	MGT	19.04±0.46a	15.34±0.51b	11.94±0.47c
	GERMend	8.36±0.13a	7.18±0.17b	5.43±0.19c
	SOEsummer	77.44±1.59a	70.13±2.34b	63.46±2.48b
	SOEend	40.15±1.73a	27.93±1.54b	16.56±1.22c
Provenance		Drier	Wetter	
	MGT	17.68±0.39a	13.2±0.42b	
	GERMend	8.1±0.12a	5.88±0.16b	
	SOEsummer	78.26±1.59a	62.42±1.88b	
	SOEend	32.7±1.39a	23.72±1.28b	

Figure 1. a) Location of the three study sites in the Iberian Peninsula; b) example of the location of the study plots at each site; c) distribution of seeding units in a plot; d) schematic illustration of a seeding unit in a burned area with Pre (simulating dispersion prior to fire) and Post (simulating dispersion postfire); and Drier and Wetter provenances. Terms are as described in the text.

Figure 2. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the interaction between the variable mean germination time (MGT) and the significant factors and interactions: site (CLIMATE), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in the three Burned pine stands in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain. Different small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups (Tukey's HSD method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described in the text.

Figure 3. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the significant interaction between the variables GERMend and the significant factors and interactions: site (CLIMATE), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in the three Burned pine stands in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain. Different small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups (Tukey's HSD method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described in the text.

Figure 4. Multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA, N=540) of the significant interaction between the variables SOEsummer and SOEend and the significant factors and interactions: site (STAND), prescription (TREATMENT) and provenance (PROV) in the three Burned pine stands in the Humid, Subhumid and dry areas of east Spain. Different small letters indicate the significant differences between the means of groups (Tukey's HSD method). Whiskers indicate standard deviation. Terms are as described in the text.

Figure 5: Number of maritime pine seedlings alive per period. Terms are as described in the text.